

tell that this causes frustration with their employers and colleagues. The frustration often spills over into their relationship, and they often argue about who should take time off work to accommodate Elsie's appointments.

Elsie and Toby attend a nursery in Doncaster 4 days a week. The nursery has an allocated worker for Elsie who she adores. Elsie is in a room with younger children, including Toby, who have a similar development level to her. She loves being at nursery and enjoys being around other children. Although she can't always join in with all the activities, Elsie loves to watch, and the nursery involve her as much as they can.

When Elsie's allocated worker is on leave or off sick, the nursery can't take Elsie. Sometimes this means that James or Lizzie need to take time off work at short notice, which is a source of frustration for them both.

“It's great that we found a nursery that could accommodate her, but we can't rely on it like other parents can”

Due to the tensions this causes with their employers, James and Lizzie have decided that one of them may need to leave work to look after Elsie full time. Financially they can't afford to do this at the moment, at least not until their house is sold. However, they worry that if something doesn't change soon that one of them may lose their job anyway due to the amount of time they are taking off work. Both worry that this will impact their ability to get another mortgage.

As Elsie is getting bigger it is becoming harder and harder for James and Lizzie to manage in their current house. Lizzie struggles to lift Elsie now and no longer feels able to carry her up and down the stairs. She recently pulled her back when lifting Elsie out of the bath.

Their home is already full of equipment for Elsie and, now that Toby is mobile, the family are running out of space. Their small living room is dominated by Elsie's specialist chair. However, Elsie prefers to be on the floor as she is able to navigate her way around the room by rolling. James and Lizzie try to keep Toby out of the living room when Elsie is there as she becomes very upset if he falls or tries to touch her or pull at her tubes. Elsie is extremely sensory and is unable to communicate or push Toby away.

“I'm not sure how much longer we can go on like this”

Elsie relies on other equipment, such as her wheelchair, specialist highchair and boxes of specialist feeding equipment which are delivered to the house. Elsie also has a BiPAP machine which she needs to wear when she goes to sleep.

Due to her digestive issues, Elsie is regularly ill and will often vomit. When Elsie is ill James and Lizzie get very little sleep as she needs to be monitored constantly as she sleeps in a BiPAP mask and could easily aspirate. Again, this causes pressures on James and Lizzie, and they often feel sleep deprived.

Lizzie's parents will often help with Toby, and he stays over with them regularly. It is harder for James and Lizzie to ask for support from family and friends with Elsie due to her complex care requirements. Lizzie and James often feel guilty that they don't spend as much time with Toby as they do with Elsie, although they know he loves being with his grandparents.

James and Lizzie pay for additional physiotherapy sessions for Elsie and are really starting to notice improvements in her muscle tone, she has recently started to sit unaided for short periods of time. This small milestone is huge progress for Elsie. James also takes Elsie swimming each week, he finds it easiest to use Armthorpe baths as it's the only one with steps into the pool to enable him to carry Elsie in and out.

“As parents of a disabled child, we don't have the power to make life “fair,” but we do try to make each day count.”

A Day in the Life of Elsie

Lizzie opens Elsie's curtains and gently calls her to wake her up. She turns off her BiPAP machine and takes off her mask. Elsie greets her mum with a big smile. Lizzie gently rubs the marks on her face left by the mask and changes her nappy.

James carries Elsie downstairs to the living room and give her some time to roll around the carpet. Elsie enjoys the familiar cartoons on CBeebies and waves her arms as the theme tunes play.

James changes Elsie's tubes and dresses her for nursery he feeds her breakfast directly into her peg, but also tries to encourage her to take a few mouthfuls of porridge. Elsie can see Lizzie giving Toby his breakfast and this encourages her to try to eat orally too.

When both children are ready, James puts Elsie into her wheelchair and fastens her into their adapted mobility car. He puts Toby in his car seat and sets out with them

both to nursery. Along the way James talks to Elsie and points out familiar landmarks on the journey. Elsie enjoys being in the new car as she can see clearly through the windows from her wheelchair.

When they arrive at nursery James is frustrated that the disabled bays are once again blocked by other parents. James has challenged them over their inconsiderate parking previously, but their response is always that they are 'just nipping in' or 'won't be 2 minutes'. James can't use any of the other bays as he can't get Elsie out of the car in her wheelchair.

James takes Elsie into her classroom and Elsie has a big smile on her face when she sees Miss Katie. James hands Miss Katie all of Elsie's equipment as well as the syringes that he has prepared with Elsie's lunch. He waves goodbye to Elsie and Toby, but they are both distracted by the busy classroom and don't even look back.

“we try to make her life as normal as it can be”

James is running late for work, due to the issues at drop off and is flustered when he arrives. He apologises to his boss and promises to work through his break.

At 1pm James gets a phone call from Nursery to say the Elsie is unwell with a high temperature and vomiting and she will need to be picked up from nursery. James tries to call Lizzie but can't reach her by phone. He has no choice but to make his apologies at work but the reception from his boss is frosty.

James considers whether to make a GP appointment. Elsie does seem poorly, but the GP is often reluctant to prescribe anything due to her complex needs and often just refers her to the hospital. Elsie has had numerous unnecessary admissions over the last 2 years. James decides to wait until the morning and try to contact her consultant. He contacts his boss to say he won't be in tomorrow.

About Elsie

Elsie is 4 years old and was born with a rare chromosomal disorder that causes developmental delay, low muscle tone and seizures, she also has digestive issues and is fed directly into her stomach via a peg. Elsie has complex needs and, as her condition is rare, little is known about her long-term prognosis.

Elsie lives with her parents James and Lizzie and younger brother Toby aged 18 months. They live in a newly built 4 bedroomed property in Rossington which they own with a mortgage. The house is currently up for sale as the family recognise that they need to move to a bungalow which they can adapt to suit Elsie's increasing needs. The house has been on the market for some time and James and Lizzie are becoming frustrated that there is little interest, despite having reduced the price twice; they put this down to the number of new builds in the area coupled with the volatile housing market and financial instability that many people are finding themselves in.

“I just wish they would Join things up a bit.... it's really stressful for her, going backwards and forwards all the time”

Elsie has to attend multiple hospital appointments due to her complex needs and James and Lizzie often find that they visit the hospital multiple times during a week, often to the same department. This has put a strain on Lizzie, who has not long been back at work after maternity leave, and James. Both have had to take many days off work for the appointments and they can

About Sofia

Sofia is 9 and lives with her parents Maria and Andrei and her Grandmother Adina. Sofia was born in Romania and moved to England wither parents when she was 4.

Sofia's parents immigrated from Romania in search of better work and more opportunities, they already had some extended family in Doncaster which is why they decided to settle here. Maria and Andrei's English is limited, and they often rely on their Sofia to translate some phrases for them when out and about in the city. This has posed some challenges for Sofia as she herself has struggled to fit in at school and make friends whilst learning a new language.

Sofia's speaks English well and although her parents speak Romanian at home, she often struggles to keep up with more formal conversations between adults.

Sofia's Grandmother moved to the UK at the same time as Sofia's parents, however she has recently been diagnosed with cancer and has moved in with the family while she undergoes treatment

Sofia's family are very religious, her grandmother in particular is very strict. Despite this they don't go to church very often as the nearest Romanian Orthodox church is in Leeds. They did go to a family wedding there recently, Sofia loved seeing the elaborately decorated interior and her parents pointed out to her the depictions of saints on the walls. Sofia felt happy there and enjoyed learning more about her culture.

Sofia attends the local primary school where she is one of the few students from a Romanian background. Sofia

knows she looks and sounds different to her peers, and at time this makes her feel different.

Sofia finds it difficult to explain her different culture to her friends and to form connections with her peers, therefore she sometimes feels isolated during group activities and struggles to express her thoughts and ideas.

Sofia's school have helped as much as they can since she joined the local primary school; she enjoys the weekly one to one session she attends which have helped her to improve her language development, however a lack of resources and specialised support has hindered her progress, and the impact of this continues to influence her confidence.

“There should be equal opportunities for all children from different backgrounds so that they have chance to mix to change the long-term future too.”

Sofia's Home

Sofia, and her family live in a private rented two-bedroom terraced house in Toll Bar. The house is need of some updating, in the kitchen and hallway some of the paint is peeling due to damp issues caused by an ongoing leak in the upstairs bathroom, despite this the house is a happy home. The walls are covered with Sofia's artwork and family photographs of Romania, offering Maria and Andrei small but comforting reminders of the place they consider home.

Maria and Andrei have tried to speak to the landlord about the issues with their home and he arranged a visit, however, they were out when he came round, and Sofia's grandmother wouldn't let him in the house without her son there. Sofia had to translate to the landlord and felt intimidated. She could tell he was annoyed that he had wasted his time.

Despite the limited space the family make the best of the room available, Sofia shares her room with her grandmother. Whilst she doesn't mind this too much, as the company can be a comfort, there are times when she wishes she had more space to play, as her house has no garden, just a small concrete yard to the rear which houses the bins. Sofia's parents often work long hours, they both deliver parcels for local logistics firms and normally work 6 days a week. Sofia often sees her classmates playing at the local park, but her parents don't like her to visit there alone

“The local park next to where I live has had swings removed and is just a mess. It has now had some tyres and a couple of benches installed and a bit of wood which says no climbing. I'm really not sure what this area is on the park and its purpose.... there's broken glass on the multi-use game area so their balls pop, dog foul all over the grass and the play part is awful. There is a small bike track but guess what, broken glass.”

A day in the life of Sofia

Sofia wakes up around 6.30am each morning to the quiet and familiar sounds of her parents chattering in Romanian and getting ready for work, her grandmother is downstairs, and the family enjoy a simple breakfast together; they try and eat at least one meal together. Maria and Andrei usually work until late into the evening; therefore, mornings are usually the only opportunity they have to spend some time as a family.

This morning, Sofia's Grandmother has received a letter from the hospital. The letter is written in English, and her parents are unable to fully understand its content. They turn to Sofia, asking her to translate the letter for them.

She reads the letter and tries her best to explain its contents. However, the letter contains complex information, which is beyond her ability to understand, and she struggles to find the correct terms in Romanian.

Sofia understands the weight of the situation, understanding that her family rely on her for information. This places a burden on her, as she grapples with the fear of making mistakes or failing to adequately assist her grandmother. Sofia is also upset by some of the information in the letters and is worried about her grandmother's deteriorating health.

As Sofia gets ready for school, she ponders her day ahead and remembers that the class will be practicing for her summer concert. Whilst Sofia is excited for the concert, she has butterflies about having to say her lines in front of her classmates.

Around 8.20am, Sofia helps her grandmother to put on her socks. She feels cold so she brings her a blanket and makes her a warm drink. She has made her own packed lunch and left a sandwich for her grandmother in the fridge. She is worried about leaving her but knows she

will be late for school if she doesn't leave soon. Sofia kisses Adina and ensures she can reach the phone before putting on her coat and leaving for school. Sofia enjoys the fresh air, even when it is cold and wet.

As Sofia enters the classroom, she feels a mixture of excitement and nervousness, she is looking forward to the rehearsal for the class play but can't help but worry about her grandmother at home. Sofia struggles to understand what the Teacher is asking and the songs in the play are difficult to learn. Her teacher notices her struggle and offers encouragement, but Sofia feels self-conscious.

“It's not just during schooltime that I worry. I can struggle to get to sleep because of the worry. This often means that I am tired too. I can over-think what could happen, and this makes me feel even more anxious.”

After a long day at school, Sofia returns home. Her Grandmother is sleeping, and Sofia checks the fridge but can see that her grandmother hasn't eaten.

Sofia worries about the play and wants to practice the lines, but it's hard with nobody around to practice with. She starts to prepare some dinner for herself whilst trying to practice singing the songs.

Maria and Andrei will not be home for some time yet. When her grandmother wakes, Sofia tells her about her day and sings her the songs from the play in a bid to improve. Sofia puts on the television, and they watch and eat together until her parents come home.

" I Know who I am"

About Alex

Alex is a 16-year-old non-binary person living in Doncaster, England. They were assigned female at birth but do not identify as strictly male or female. Alex has known about their non-binary identity since they were 14, and they came out to their close friends and family shortly after. However, they have yet to come out to their wider community due to fear of potential discrimination and lack of understanding.

Alex lives with their parents and a younger sister, Emily, in a modest three-bedroom house in a residential neighbourhood of Doncaster. Their Mum, Sarah, and Stepdad, Mark, are supportive and loving, but they have limited knowledge and understanding of LGBTQ+ identities and struggles. They are open to learning and trying their best to support Alex, although they sometimes struggle with fully grasping non-binary concepts.

"Female pronouns didn't feel OK.... I never minded he/him, but it also didn't feel quite right."

Alex's Mum and Stepdad have been accepting of their non-binary identity since they came out to them. However, they sometimes unintentionally use the wrong pronouns or struggle to remember to address Alex in gender-neutral terms. They are learning to navigate this new territory and often rely on Alex's guidance to better understand their experiences.

On occasion, Alex will hear their parents misgender them to health professionals or schoolteachers. Although Alex knows that their parents support them,

Alex still finds this hard to hear and it effects their self-confidence and identity.

"If you met me, you might not know if I'm a girl or a boy. And you would be right. I'm neither. I am nonbinary."

While Alex's home is generally a safe space, there are occasional moments of tension or discomfort. Alex's Father in particular struggles to accept their gender and will often insist on sending Alex very feminine cards and gifts for birthdays as well as referring to them by their dead name. Alex overheard their father complaining to their Mum that this was all a phase and that Alex's Mum shouldn't encourage it. As a result of these tensions, Alex has a strained relationship with their dad and currently refuses to see him.

Alex often feels pressure to conform to societal expectations when interacting with relatives and feels uneasy during family gatherings.

Alex shares a close bond with their younger sister, Emily, who is 13 years old. Emily is more knowledgeable and accepting of LGBTQ+ identities due to her exposure to progressive ideas at school and through social media. She actively supports Alex and often stands up for them when they face discrimination or ignorance. Their sibling relationship provides a source of comfort and understanding for Alex, and they frequently have open conversations about gender identity and equality.

"People of our generation are going to accept [my sexuality] because it is just normal...you see things every day where people are gay, they're talking about their pansexuality, their asexuality...just difficulty seeing whether parents think the same..."

Alex has decorated their bedroom with artwork, and books that reflect diverse identities. It serves as a personal sanctuary where they can fully express their true self without fear of judgment or misunderstanding.

"I researched online and learned about different identities, that being nonbinary actually existed. Looking at people's experiences, I realised that I was similar to them."

Overall, while there may be occasional misunderstandings or lack of awareness, Alex's home provides a generally supportive and loving environment.

School Life and Community Experiences

Alex attends a medium-sized secondary school in Doncaster. The school, like many others in Doncaster is strict and enforces pupils to conform to its strict standards, not leaving much room for individuals to express their identities.

Alex was given their first strike for not conforming to the uniform policy for wearing a rainbow wristband to school, which they had forgotten to remove after attending pride festival with their parents. Alex received a 30-minute detention following their second strike for turning up in trainers; Alex's Mum had written a note to explain that their school shoes were wet from walking home in the rain the previous day, but the school would not accept it. Alex has been warned they may face an exclusion if it happens again.

The staff have limited understanding of non-binary identities and struggles, resulting in an environment that often feels unwelcoming and isolating for Alex.

Alex faces various challenges in their interactions with peers. While some classmates are accepting and supportive, others perpetuate ignorance and discrimination. Finding genuine and understanding friends within the school community can be a struggle.

"My gender identity is a big part of who I am, but I'm scared to come out to everyone. I've heard stories of people being bullied or rejected, and I don't want to face that."

Alex can have struggles with their mental health which is sometimes exacerbated by the comments from their peers; recently Alex has cut themselves as a way to relive tension following altercations with some kids at school. The physical pain of hurting themselves felt like a distraction from the emotional pain they were struggling with. Alex tends to confide in friends online about their hardships and they often share similar experiences.

"Sometimes I go online and connect with other people who feel like I do. It's comforting to know I'm not alone and to talk to others who understand what I'm going through."

At school, Alex attends classes where they often feel like an outsider. The curriculum at Alex's school rarely acknowledges LGBTQ+ experiences, leaving them feeling invisible and marginalized. They hear derogatory comments and sniggering from other pupils as they walk through school and face misgendering, from both pupils and staff.

"For me, being misgendered as a boy is much better than being misgendered as a girl."

PE lessons are especially challenging, as the school insists that Alex use the female changing room and do PE with the Girls. Alex will often ask their Mum to write a note for PE, excusing them for having an injury; more recently Alex has skipped school altogether on PE days. They recently received a warning for their attendance.

There are no dedicated LGBTQ+ clubs or groups, making it challenging for Alex to connect with other LGBTQ+ students who share similar experiences. The absence of safe spaces or inclusive policies within the school exacerbates feelings of isolation and hinders opportunities for personal growth and support.

Alex faces challenges beyond the school environment, such as encountering prejudice in public. These negative experiences contribute to a sense of not fully belonging or being understood within their own community.

Due to the lack of public understanding, Alex is cautious about disclosing their non-binary identity to the wider community. Fear of potential discrimination, judgment, or harassment keeps them from being open about their true self outside of their immediate circle of friends and family.

"We just bottle it up...can't really talk about it to friends because you don't know what they will say if that gets passed around or the 'wrong' kind of people find out"

Navigating school life and community experiences is a constant challenge for Alex, as they strive for acceptance, understanding, and representation in environments that often lack these crucial elements.

"I'm always on guard, trying to be careful about how I express my gender. I want to be myself, but I also don't want to draw too much attention or face discrimination."

‘I had no choice about coming into care – it’s not something I asked for, it was something that happened to me’.

About Kirsty

Kirsty is 22-years old and experienced an often-turbulent and uncertain childhood due to domestic violence in her family.

Kirsty's mother Amy, struggled with substance abuse, which exacerbated an often-challenging environment at home.

As a result, Kirsty was placed in care at the age of 10, following multiple incidents of physical abuse and witnessing her parents' volatile relationship.

Kirsty's journey through care consisted of several placements as she struggled to find stability and a sense of belonging. She experienced feelings of abandonment, loneliness, and rejection, leading to difficulties in forming trusting relationships with her foster families.

Due to the constant changes in her living arrangements, her challenges in dealing with her past and her feelings around this, Kirsty has developed various mental health issues, including anxiety and depression which have led to previous A&E admissions.

‘As soon as it was mentioned that I was a care experienced person attending with carers from my children’s home I was ushered into a room that is used for prisoners! It was hurtful and unnecessary and left me feeling degraded and pretty

rubbish about myself at a time when what I really needed was care and support. It’s not right to make a person feel so devalued and it feels very unfair.’

Trying to access support for her mental health has been hard work, her GP has been supportive but

“The waiting lists for mental health services are way too long”.

Kirsty is heavily pregnant with her first child and is due to give birth in the Autumn. Kirsty feels unsupported and feels that the people around her have been negative about her pregnancy. No one has congratulated her or told her that she will be cared for. The only people she feels supported by are her friends and other care experienced people.

Kirsty’s home:

Since leaving her supported accommodation, Kirsty lives in a small, one bedroom flat in the Cantley and she is currently preparing for the arrival of her baby who will share her bedroom. Whilst Kirsty wishes things could be different, she is proud of her home and determined to offer her baby the stability she craved whilst growing up.

The living room is small and has a worn-out sofa donated to Kirsty by a friend’s Mum, a coffee table, and a television. The walls are tired, with peeling paint and visible signs of dampness. The carpet is stained however Kirsty has managed to disguise this with a rug. The window frames are old and drafty allowing cold air and noise from the road below to seep in.

Although the bathroom is useable it requires updating. The tiles are cracked in places and the grout is discoloured. A lack of adequate ventilation has led to a permanent, musty smell.

The flat is on the third floor of the building and Kirsty is aware of the issue she will have carrying a pushchair up and down the stairs as the building’s lift is frequently out of order. She has mentioned her situation to the housing association however she has been advised that she isn’t a priority.

A day in the life of Kirsty:

Kirsty wakes early to the familiar baby kicks she has been experiencing for some time and whilst she already loves her unborn child she often feels overwhelmed by a sense of impending responsibility. Kirsty has never had

to care for anyone other than herself and is anxious about how she will cope.

Although the father of the baby is aware that Kirsty is pregnant, Kirsty has little contact with him following a disagreement that turned violent. Despite his assurances that this would never happen again Kirsty is unsure about what to do for the best. This confusion worries Kirsty as she knows he could turn up at any time to see the baby once it is born.

Kirsty gets out of bed, turns on the Television and makes herself a cup of tea with a couple of biscuits for breakfast before getting dressed for her appointment with her Midwife. As Kirsty gets dressed, she recollects her experience at her pre-birth assessment and deliberately chooses a top with long sleeves to hide the scars on her arms caused by previous self-harm.

‘To be honest the [pre-birth assessment] was challenging to say the least. It did not feel like it came from a supportive place and made me feel like I was again being judged for my experience of being in care and having to battle to prove myself a person worthy of keeping their child.’

Although Kirsty likes her Midwife, she is weary of her and feels as though she treats her differently, she recalls the time told her Midwife she was care experienced and the way she felt her attitude towards her changed. She looked at her differently, she spoke to her differently, and not always in a bad way. Sometimes it was patronising, and sometimes it was with pity but it always differently.

‘Throughout my pregnancy I was always open and honest about my care experience with everyone who asked. The doctors, the midwives – everyone really. I have been told so many times that I should not be ashamed, that growing up in care was not my fault – yet I am punished, discriminated against, and judged by society and often by the very people who are there to care for me.’

After her appointment, Kirsty walks the short distance home and grabs another couple of biscuits for lunch, and although Kirsty knows she is underweight and should be eating more healthily, she is conscious about

spending too much of her benefit on things like food as she wants to save as much as she can for the baby. Kirsty dreams of getting a job to support herself and the baby once it arrives but with little childcare support, she knows this will be hard.

As Kirsty folds up some of the clothes, she has been gifted for her baby she reflects on her past and remembers the times she was told by other children at school that she was not loved by her parents because she was in care. Kirsty remembers with sadness how she was never invited to birthday parties, to sleepovers, and how keenly she felt this. She recalls how from a distance, she had watched her peers grow up feeling secure, happy, and having fun – everything that a childhood should be.

‘This was damaging and debilitating for me, and I know will stay with me for a lifetime. I never felt supported by teachers, it was just something that I had to get on with and accept. Kids will be kids and all that. But I should not have just had to accept this. It’s not right and it’s definitely not fair!’

Kirsty opens her post and finds another water bill; this is the third she has received as she has ignored the previous ones. She doesn’t understand why the bills are increasing and she is unsure where to go for help. Kirsty folds up the bill and puts it away.

With an increasing sense of anxiety and unease, Kirsty tries to distract herself, but with a little money to spare, time seems to pass slowly. Kirsty isn’t used to the quiet and can’t wait until the baby arrives so that she can sit and cuddle it all day rather than feeling, unseen, unheard and unloved.

At 7pm, Kirsty makes herself some tea, baked beans on toast and watches TV for a while. She loves Emmerdale and waiting for it to start gives her something to look forward too. After it has finished, she decides to head to bed as she cold and tired, however she knows that like most nights she will find it hard to get to sleep as she still struggles with nightmares related to the domestic violence she witnessed as a child.

“sometimes I wonder if they would just be better off without me”

About Kate, Max & Grace

Kate is 35 years old and, for the last 3 years has been a single parent to Max aged 9 and Grace aged 7. Both children attend a primary school near their home in Bentley, Doncaster.

Kate separated from her ex-partner after his drinking increased and he became abusive. When bailiffs started to arrive at her home, Kate discovered that he had been hiding a gambling addiction. Eventually their home was repossessed by the bank.

Max and Grace were extremely upset by their parents' separation. Max had witnessed his parents arguing a lot and started having problems at school as well as becoming extremely withdrawn at home. Grace would be heartbroken every time their father missed a visit and Kate would make excuses that he must have been held up at work.

After she first moved out Kate tried to ensure that the children still had regular contact with their father, but his visits became sporadic and eventually stopped altogether. Kate didn't attempt to contact him, and he didn't contact them either. When the visits stopped, Kate felt that things settled somewhat at home and didn't want to pursue her ex for maintenance payments for fear he would start upsetting the children again. She also knew that his addictions had worsened and wasn't exactly sure how to contact him anyway.

Kate now works full time (term-time) as an admin assistant at a primary school in Warmsworth. Kate's job allows her to spend weekends and school holidays with her children. She enjoys working and the social interaction with her colleagues.

After their separation, Kate approached the Council to see if they could help her with housing. Unfortunately, due to her mortgage arrears, she was told that she didn't qualify for Social Housing and had to move in

with her parents for a time. Eventually, she found a house to rent, and her brother agreed to act as guarantor. Although the rent is more than she can really afford, she hasn't been able to find anywhere cheaper and she is worried that the landlord may increase the rent further.

“I was so embarrassed going in to ask for help, and I felt so exposed... like a goldfish sat in front of that window...for everyone walking past to stare at”

Kate now rents a small, 3-bedroom terraced property on Kirkby Avenue in Bentley. She has a small car that belonged to her grandfather. Her mum gave it to her when he passed away and it's a lifeline for Kate, she would not be able to get to and from work and juggle the kids without it.

“The housing list does not take into account single parents who live in costly private rented houses who are desperately struggling to pay costs.”

Despite working, Kate's budget is extremely tight. She has just £27.64 a week left after essential spending. She is limited as to what other work she can pursue as she would struggle to afford childcare. Kate does receive Universal credit and gets single person reduction on her council tax, but as she is working, she isn't entitled to other support such as free school meals

Kate is struggling to manage paying her new bills whilst also struggling to pay the debts from her previous relationship. Kate has tried to negotiate with some of the debt companies, arguing that some of the debt should be recovered from her ex, but the companies have told Kate that she is liable as her partner can't be found.

Kate has unplugged her house phone as she was mostly receiving calls from debt collection agencies, and she has stopped opening her post as she feels she can't deal with it anymore. Kate worries about people coming to the house and often won't answer the door if the caller is unexpected, she mostly keeps the curtains closed when she is at home. This has become a major cause of anxiety for Kate, and she worries that it's affecting her children. Sometimes she has snapped at them for playing around the curtains or being loud when someone is at the door.

Kate doesn't often socialise with friends anymore; she can't really afford to go out and is embarrassed about not being able to afford things. She has started to avoid other parents in the playground at school as they often speak about holidays they are going on or places they are taking their children. Although Kate doesn't feel jealous, she resents the conversation as she knows she can't afford these things for her own children.

Kate knows that her money problems and anxieties are having an impact on her children too. Max has asked to play football for the local team and is really enjoying football at school, but Kate just can't afford it. Similarly, Grace would like to go to dance class with her friends, but it's just too expensive. Kate will often decline the invitations her children receive for birthday parties, making the excuse that they are staying over at Nana's house or have family commitments. In reality, Kate can't really afford the gift that she believes would be expected or bring herself to make small talk with the other Mums.

“Access to activities for wellbeing / craft always seem to be in the day not taking into account working families who also need support.”

Kate does her best to make sure the children get out and about as much as possible, she will often encourage them to play in the garden or go to the park. Kate will try and access the free things that she sees advertised by the council on Facebook, but they are often in the town centre and does not always feel safe.

“Unfair that I don't feel safe as a female to go into town now with my children due to antisocial behaviour - ie begging, drug addicts”

She is concerned about Max's weight. She recently received a letter from the school nursing team informing her that he was over-weight. This adds to Kate's anxieties that she is having a negative impact on her children. She knows they would love to play sports and that their diets could be better. Kate is already only eating one meal a day to try and make ends meet and fresh food seems to be so much more expensive.

Kate has recently been called into school to discuss Max's behaviour. School staff have become worried about him recently as he seems to be acting out and has been getting into altercations with other children. The school ask probing questions about Max's homelife, and Kate feels embarrassed and guilty about her situation.

A Day in the life of Kate Max and Grace

Kate silences the alarm on her phone and forces her eyes open, she feels exhausted as she only got a few hours' sleep between worrying over the events of the day before.

Today is the last day of school term and Kate just wants to get through the day. She gets ready for work before waking up Max, Grace is already downstairs and watching cartoons.

Kate makes herself a quick cup of coffee before setting the kids clothes out, Max put a hole in his trousers yesterday playing football and he doesn't have a clean

pair. She puts out a pair of his old ones, but he gets angry with her as they are too short. Kate tells him it will have to be those or the ones with a hole which starts a tantrum, Max starts throwing things and telling his Mum how much he hates her.

Kate digs through the wash basket hurriedly trying to find a pair of Max's trousers that might do for the last day and manages to pull out a pair with a small grass stain on the knee...she throws them at Max and snaps at him to hurry up and get dressed. Kate feels on edge and feels the lump rising in her throat.

Back downstairs Grace has put on her shirt and skirt but is back watching cartoons, Kate shouts at her and turns the tv off and Grace scoots off to find her socks. Kate empties both school bags and finds Grace's cardigan screwed up and covered in beans. She does her best to sponge them off but doesn't have time to get the Iron out. She needs to get them to breakfast club or she will be late for work.

There are several letters in the school bags, one about a residential trip for Max next school year. The trip is £125 payable in instalments but the first £50 needs to be paid by next term. Kate sets the letter down, knowing she will have to ask her parents if they can help. The other letter is a sponsor form for Grace for a fun run to raise money for school funds. It also says she will need a green t-shirt for the day as the children will be running in their house colours.

“It just feels like school want money all the time. It's never ending”

Kate ushers the kids into the car, Grace is complaining that her shoes are too tight, and Max is angry with Kate and drags his feet. Kate can feel her temper starting to fray but takes a deep breath and reminds herself it's the last day.

On the short drive to school Grace asks her Mum if they are going to the school fair after school. Kate snaps “we'll see” and tells Grace she is very busy at work; Kate knows she doesn't have enough spare money for the school fair and she can't deal with the looks from other parents. Grace persists; she has decorated a plant pot at school, and they will be selling them at the fair for £3. She is scared that someone else will buy her plant pot that she made for Mummy. Kate tries to placate Grace and tells her she will call Nana to see if she can take them to the fair.

Kate drops the kids at breakfast club and drives to work. She sits for a moment in the car to regain her composure before calling her Mum about the school fair. She agrees to take them and then take them back to her house for tea.